
EXPLORING THE POTENTIAL OF OPEN DATA: FROM ONGOING PRACTICES TO FUTURE SCENARIOS.

Workshop organisers:

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WORKSHOP PRESENTATION

With the digitalization of services and research data collection in the public space; as well as with the paradigm of the Internet of Things where more and more data from daily activities are collected in several ways, opening up this richness has become a social endeavour. In this context, the assumption that open data can encompass different forms of learning, or that they could be adopted in educational scenarios appears as a natural consequence (Raffaghelli, 2017). There are rich existing educational practices that have been characterized, and approaches for educational applications of open data are being explored (Atenas, Havemann, & Priego, 2015). Moreover, some have discussed the relevance of this approach under the lens of critical pedagogy, emphasizing the importance of open data for social cohesion (Manca, Atenas, Ciociola, & Nascimbeni, 2017). However, an important challenge for the societies to mine the treasure of open data, in a context of Open Education, regards the analytical basis and frameworks for practice that support mainstreaming. This has been a concern for the **Network “Open Education Italy” that launched the project “ODA - Open Data per l’Apprendimento”**. This workshop is an activity of the network and aims at exploring the educational potential of Open Data in diversified contexts of learning: formal (school and higher education) non-formal (work) and informal (political activism and civic engagement).

- The workshop's target are not only researchers but also practitioners interested on understanding the concept of open data connected to lifelong learning, as well as designing educational interventions adopting Open Data.
- The workshop will be organized in two simple phases:
 - 1- A conceptual introduction, which will put the basis to understand and discover the principles, the policy context and the existing practices relating Open Data, together with cases addressing practices
 - 2- A “hands on” moment in which the concepts above will be applied to the participants’ pedagogical practices, and their sense discussed on the light of both practical and deontological implications.

The topics that will be presented during the first part of the workshop, guiding reflection, will be:

What is an Open Educational Resource and why Open Data could apply? The central thesis discussed will deal with the need of exploring the specific characteristics of Open Data in the light of the already well-known issues and constrains regarding Open Educational Resources, to integrate them as particular category.

Open Data as Open Educational Resources: a model to train educators. Open Data can be key in the development of transversal skills (including digital and data literacies, alongside skills for critical thinking, research, teamwork, and global citizenship), enhancing students’ abilities to understand and select information sources, to work with, curate, analyse and interpret data, and to conduct and evaluate research. This idea will be discussed along several examples for practice.

Open data as a plea to promote open knowledge and participative continuous learning in local health-care settings. The presentation describes an innovative activity run in the health-care system in the city of Ferrara, between 2015 and 2017, and promoted by the Region Emilia-Romagna. A researcher observed and ethnographically described the cultural and the organizational changes in a local health-care setting during an experimental learning activity aimed to change the internal and the institutional communication of the local public health-care services, including the access to open datasets in Health-care.

Learning in the datafied society: from informal to formal learning, a critical perspective. Overall, in this presentation it will be underlined the fact that living in the *datafied* society could encompass for children and adults more surveillance and exploitation by those controlling/showing data, instead of more empowerment. However, the audience attention will be driven onto the potential of education and training to heal the above mentioned issues. Three cases will be considered in order to trigger the audience's reactions.

NOTES FROM THE FIELD

Juliana E. Raffaghelli

The workshop was held on June 18 at 17hs. It was not an ideal time to gain the audience attention. As in other cases, the participants could be divided between those actually motivated and interested on the topic, and some just willing to change from traditional presentations to more active engagement.

There were 8 participants, 2 males and 6 females from: Italy (2), Sweden, UK, Spain (2) and Croatia. The mentioned backgrounds were mostly from education sciences, adults' education, social networks, open education, instructional design. Due to the problems of connection, even if I had prepared some online interaction, I preferred to deliver as a dialogic presentation in a plenary session. I could observe that half of the participants were active while the rest were rather shy and observed the interactions. The most confident participants were both males and females, from expert to highly expert according to an initial round table. All in all, the 8 participants could be placed between 40 to 55 years old, so in any case they were senior educators (working in contexts of EU networks and projects) and researchers in educational technologies. Four of them worked with higher education, and the rest spanned from teachers' education to professional learning in non-formal and informal settings.

The first interaction was the self-analysis of data literacy. I carried out this exercise not only because for the participants it could be interesting to explore their own levels of literacy, but mainly because I was offering a tool which could be adopted by them in their educational practices. As said, I did not ask to complete the self-diagnosis by using the online tool, but showed them the several questions and they decided (as group) where they could be placed.

I will now introduce the figures with the overall rating self-assigned as group (a sort of "dialogic mean score") and the discussion connected to it.

To which extent are you able of critically searching and selecting data?

Please select only one answer

Zero	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Specialised
I do not have enough knowledge or competence to indicate any option.	I am aware of the importance of data for research and communication. I acknowledge the areas within a project of mine which need data.	I am able to individuate the type of data (graphs/tables/schemes) that I can use to illustrate my project.	I am able to read graphs and tables elaborated by other students. I am able to evaluate their adequacy with respect to the general asset of the project.	I am able to analyze groups of graphs and tables. I am able to critically evaluate the adequacy with regard to a scientific, historic, social, etc., communication.

Most participants felt very comfortable with this area of data literacy (but you might notice they decided to place themselves somewhere between 3 and 4, Advanced to Specialised). Some of them, working in the field of research commented on the use of advanced tools to read and produce data visualizations. However, they pointed out how difficult this might be amongst the learners they usually deal with in the contexts of practice. There was agreement on

the relevance of promoting “good data readers”. The participants felt comfortable with their role as eventual educators in this area, though some of them pointed out at the need of more research on the new informational contexts with complex interactive data visualizations.

To which extent are you able to mine the data of your interest?

Zero	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Specialised
I do not have enough knowledge or competence to indicate any option.	I am aware data can be found online and can be downloaded for personal use. I am able to surf and individuate the types of digital content (e.g. files) where there the data needed can be found.	I am able to access the digital content where I can find the data needed. I am able to prepare data as dataset for further analysis.	I am able to find different types of digital content. I am able to integrate the reformulated content in dataset so as to prepare it to different forms of further analysis.	I am able to elaborate queries for the specific research of digital content. I am able to choose and integrate the content found in one or more datasets for further analysis.

Also in this case the participants pointed out that within their work they frequently collected data through several means. However, in this case there was much “variance” in the responses, since some of the participants were less convinced about their actual ability to “surf and individuate several types of digital content with embedded data”. There was a good debate about what is data and to which extent data is only quantitative. When embracing a broader definition of data, the participants felt more comfortable and able of carrying out more operations (“preparing a corpus is like preparing a dataset”). Only one of the participants (senior researcher) felt in the position of choosing and integrating the content found in one or more datasets for further analysis. Of course, teaching or supporting learning on around this set of skills was even more complex. Only two of the participants had experience in coaching research assistants in collecting data and elaborating datasets. In educational contexts, one question was at which levels of education these skills should be taught.

To which extent are you able of managing your data digital contexts?

Zero	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Specialised
I do not have enough knowledge or competence to indicate any option.	I am aware it is important to organize and protect data. I am able to use basic digital tools locally so as to organize data found online.	I am able to use basic digital tools locally so as to organize and protect data found online. I am able to individuate datasets which contain sensitive data.	I am able to use basic digital tools locally or in the cloud so as to organize and protect data found online. I am able to anonymise sensitive data in a dataset.	I am able to use basic digital tools locally or in the cloud so as to organize and protect data found online. I am able to reformulate sensitive data in a dataset to make them open.

The results for this set of skills was the same than the prior. Some participants were actually curious about the concept of “managing data”, since for them data is to be collected or analysed, but, what is in-between those two stages?

Data protection and anonymisation was a huge issue of debate. All the participants were aware of the emerging problem of data usage and data protection (the recently embraced GDPR was thrown into the discussion). However, some thought that data should be collected for educational and research purposes without limitations, whereas other considered the problem of surveillance and particularly of the problem of continuous data tracking by social media. Moreover, this is part of the data “restricted/closed” to which nobody will have access except those in privileged positions. The participants felt in a sort of dilemma where the educators cannot have access to the needed data, there are ethical concern about having such access, but others, less protective than an educator, can have illimited access. How and what to teach about privacy and students’ data usage? This question remained as THE question, unanswered by the purposes of the workshop, which focus was to work on that part of the data which is accessible and for good purposes, not surveillance.

To which extent are you able of communicating and cooperating using data in digital contexts?

Zero	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Specialised
I do not have enough knowledge or competence to indicate any option.	I am aware of the existence of digital environments where data can be analyzed in a cooperative manner. I am able to indicate to other group colleagues where they can find useful data for an ongoing project.	I am able to individuate web/social environments or digital libraries where open data can be found. I am able to individuate the communication tools provided to share information or to make questions about data.	I am able to participate (register, post on forums, etc.) within web/social environments or digital libraries where open data can be found. I am able to share my data with other peers I know.	I have been/am active on some web/social environments or digital libraries where open data can be found. I am able to share my open data with other members of the digital community. I am able to open my data for the further cooperation.

The collaborative engagement with data was puzzling for the participants. Most of them declared to use Drive or the email to share datasets, and asked what was “open data repositories and libraries”. Surprisingly, there was very little knowledge about Open Data Government and for most participants (7), it was the first notice of the OECD-PISA datasets as example of educational open data. Two participants mentioned the National Statistics agencies and the EUROSTAT as places were to search open data, but they could not imagine other means to share or co-work over these datasets unless it was using Drive, Dropbox, email, or the shared server at work (with physical location at work).

Then somebody brought to the discussion ResearchGate as academic social network where data could be shared (there is indeed a new feature, dataset, which can be associated to the main publication shared). I recalled to all the participants that ResearchGate was flexible in nature, but private as platform, and hence with terms of use that might be dangerous at the time of data usages, aligning with the prior discussion. The participants were not aware about this fact, but agreed on the need of raising awareness amongst educators and researchers: ResearchGate is highly used and its popularity is even growing. “Can we use something that is private (ResearchGate) as public (sharing our information openly on the web)? I think this is a sort of oxymoron...” that was the reflection of one of the participants.

To which extent are you able of presenting data (storytelling with data) creatively in digital contexts?

Zero	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Specialised
I do not have enough knowledge or competence to indicate any option.	I am aware of the importance of using data critically so as to substantiate one's communication. I am able to use digital tools (apps and softwares) to create visualizations on my data. I am able to use the statistical language and the basic graphic organizers for the visualizations.	I am able to integrate visualizations created with digital tools (apps and softwares) into infographic representations. I am able to use softwares and apps for the digital infographic representations. I am able to use the statistical language and the advanced graphic organizers for the visualizations.	I am able to use apps and softwares for the visualization and the creation of infographic representations with statistical/ numerical elements, or elements of interactive graphic modeling.	I am able to create advanced digital tools/interfaces for the visualization of infographic representations with statistical/ numerical elements, or elements of interactive graphic modeling.

0 1 2 3 4

Zero Specialised

When arrived to this question, most participants were pretty sure that was not their area of expertise and that they would have needed from a programmer to develop dynamic visualizations or infographies. They agreed however that basic skills of data storytelling were very interesting at school and professional development, since everything has become “so visual”. The participants asked for examples of basic tools that could be adopted in education to promote data storytelling. There was some awareness of tools for advanced data science (two participants knew Python as software being used, not as users of it).

To which extent are you able of using Open Data to teach?

Zero	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Specialised
I do not have enough knowledge or competence to indicate any option.	I have explored Open Data portals *OR* I generate my own Open Data ...but I still do not find a feasible way to design and implement learning activities based on Open Data. I am aware of the opportunity of using open data as authentic resources to teach.	I have explored Open Data portals *OR* I got to know about educational experiences with Open Data *OR* I generate my own Open Data and I have ideas to use it in educational contexts. *AND* I am designing or have ideas to design learning activities adopting Open Data as the base for authentic problems to learn.	I know very well and I have used Open Data Portals *OR* I have been engaged in projects using Open Data for learning. *OR* I generate my own Open Data *AND* I have designed and implemented learning activities adopting Open Data as the base for authentic problems to learn.	I know very well and I have used Open Data Portals *OR* I have been engaged in projects using Open Data for learning. *OR* I generate my own Open Data *AND* I have trained/coached others in designing and implementing learning activities adopting Open Data as the base for authentic problems to learn

Finally, there was a direct question on Open Data to teach and learn. At this point, the participants were rather sceptical about their own skills, but confident about their capacity to develop them and apply them in their fields of knowledge. However, most participants (6) felt at the point of awareness relating the opportunity of using open data as authentic resources and a small group (2) said they could design for learning after the conversation held during the workshop.

To keep on exploring the potential of Open Data, I then proposed an Open Data expedition. A number of open data portals were offered

- The European Data Portal - <https://www.europeandataportal.eu/>
- The OECD Data Portal - <https://data.oecd.org/>
- The UNESCO Data Portal - <https://opendata.unesco.org/>
- Proposal of exploring Open Government Portals (your city, your region, your country).

We then discussed the following issues:

[Formal Learning]

- In which extent the concept of open data could be applied to my (workshop's participant) pedagogical practices?
- Which sets of data could be useful for me?
- Which are the critical issues that I could face to implement open data in my pedagogical practices?

[Non-formal and Informal learning]

- Which types of learning processes are triggered by open data? How could I recognize non-formal and informal learning with Open Data?
- Which are the critical issues that could face in my attempt to recognize the learning outputs in activities with Open Data?

Much of the content of these questions had been discussed during the self-assessment exercise. What it was surprising for the participants was the richness of open data that they could find by navigating the open portals. The European Data portal looked interesting, though most participants referred that it was difficult to navigate and extract relevant data for their teaching. Another relevant issue was the time needed to prepare an eventual dataset for teaching and developing data literacy in the contexts of reference. One participant referred that since she worked in the field of teachers' training she would have repeated the same structure of the current workshop. Another explained that working with undergraduates in the field of education, she would have selected the OECD portal to navigate and understand the PISA results. Yet other two participants, working in the field of professional learning, considered highly interesting to develop activities relating reading and interpreting basic data, as well as presenting or even generating basic data visualization. One of the problems observed in middle management and workers in services sectors is the rigid interpretation of data, sticking to traditions of communication. Moreover, data gets "dispersed" without relevant sharing, collaboration and appropriation within the organizational culture.

There was little time left to comment on recognition, which in any case was considered very interesting in contexts of vocational and professional development. I hence mentioned "hackathons" and "datathons" as strategy adopted by the Open Knowledge Foundation, and the participants were enthusiastic. However, which data, to which levels of literacy was an issue: the participants' targets (according to their opinion) were not able of participating in open hackathons. The materials should be produced to trigger relevant reflections and engagement with data, with the risk of failure due to the technical complexity of extracting, managing, elaborating and presenting data.

As I concluded the workshop I asked to myself which could be done to develop further the topic. I noticed that Open Data was just the peak of an iceberg and that there were issues of data literacy connected to invisible or restricted data (not Open) requiring attention. Particularly, a critical approach to data in order to understand the technical side to include into stories, narratives and as overall part of meaning making processes appeared as a relevant endeavor for the educators.